

TORORO CEMENT LIMITED

(Formally Tororo Cement Industries Limited)

KAMPALA OFFICE:
P.O. Box 22753 Kampala
Tel: +256 (414) 250065 / 71
+256 (312) 260183 / 184
Fax: +256 (414) 344564
GODOWN 6th Street
Tel: +256 (772) 967836
NAMANVE GODOWN
Tel: +256 (772) 565447
Week No: 8

TORORO FACTORY:
P.O. Box 74 , Tororo , Uganda
Tel: +256 (454) 448025 / 75
+256 (352) 512500 (PBX)
Fax: +256 (352) 512517
Email : tcl@tororocement.com
MALABA:
Tel: +256 (454) 442481
Fax: +256 (454) 442278
17.02.2025

CUSTOMER : General
CEMENT TYPE: PORTLAND CEMENT :CEM I 42.5N
STANDARD SPECIFICATION: US EAS 18-1:2017 CEM I 42.5N ; Equivalence: EN 197-1
VESSEL'S NAME: **DESTINATION:** GENERAL

CHEMICAL ANALYSIS			
PARAMETER	SPECIFICATION	UNIT	RESULTS
Sulphuric Anhydride (SO ₃)	MAX : 3.50		1.70
Chloride	MAX : 0.10		0.007
L.O.I	MAX; 5.0		1.89
I.R.	MAX; 5.0		0.56
Total alkali Na equivalent	NR		0.567
Al ₂ O ₃	MAX: 8.0	%	4.37
Fe ₂ O ₃	-		4.21
CaO	-		64.17
MgO	MAX: 3.0		1.36
Na ₂ O	-		0.33
K ₂ O	-		0.36
C ₃ A	-		4.457
PHYSICAL TESTS			
TEST	SPECIFICATION	UNIT	RESULTS
Fineness (Blaine) .	NR	M ² / Kg	345.6
Setting Time			
(a) Initial	MIN. : 60	Minutes	150
(b) Final	MAX: 600	Minutes	240
Soundness by Lechatilier	MAX 10.0	mm	0.0
Compressive strength			
(a) 48 +/- 1 hour	MIN;10.0	Mpa	18.95
(b) 168 +/- 2 hours	NR	Mpa	31.74
(c) 672 +/- 4 hours	MIN : 42.5	Mpa	45.86

REMARKS: The certificate represents dispatch for Batch No. 17.02.2025.

Nuss

Bhadresh Bhatt
Manager (QC & QA)

PRODUCER & MANUFACTURERS OF :

Portland Cement , galvanised corrugated Iron Sheets,
Ridges & Gutters , Wire nails & Wire Products

